

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF TGF- β 1 GENE POLYMORPHISM IN THE CLINICAL COURSE AND TREATMENT OF SYSTEMIC SCLERODERMA

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ABSTRACT

Systemic scleroderma is a chronic autoimmune disease of connective tissue, characterized by progressive fibrosis, microangiopathy and immune disorders. In recent years, the importance of cytokines regulating fibrogenesis, in particular TGF- β 1, in the pathogenesis of the disease has been increasing. The aim of this study is to assess the effect of TGF- β 1 gene polymorphism on the clinical course and severity of the disease in patients with systemic scleroderma. 30 patients and 10 healthy individuals as a control group were involved in the study. All participants underwent clinical, laboratory and molecular genetic examinations. The distribution of TGF- β 1 gene polymorphisms and their association with clinical symptoms, organ involvement, and disease severity were analyzed. According to the results, TGF- β 1 gene polymorphisms were found to be more common in patients with systemic scleroderma and were associated with fibrotic changes, diffuse form, and lung involvement. The obtained data showed that TGF- β 1 gene polymorphisms have important clinical significance in assessing the prognosis of the disease and choosing an individual treatment strategy.

Introduction

Systemic scleroderma is one of the severe autoimmune diseases of connective tissue, characterized by the development of progressive fibrosis in the skin and internal organs. Although the etiology of the disease is not fully understood, genetic predisposition, immunological disorders, and microangiopathy are considered important pathogenetic factors. Cytokines, especially transforming growth factor- β 1, play a leading role in the development of the fibrosis process. TGF- β 1 enhances the activation of fibroblasts, increases collagen synthesis, and leads to the accumulation of extracellular matrix. Excessive activation of this cytokine signaling pathway causes the development of fibrosis of the skin and internal organs in systemic scleroderma. In recent years, the effect of TGF- β 1 gene polymorphisms on cytokine production and their relationship with disease severity have been widely studied. Identification of genetic markers is important for assessing the prognosis of the disease, early

diagnosis, and choosing individual treatment tactics. Therefore, studying the relationship of TGF- β 1 gene polymorphisms with the clinical course in systemic scleroderma is an urgent scientific and clinical problem. This study aimed to determine the clinical significance of TGF- β 1 gene polymorphism in patients with systemic scleroderma. Systemic scleroderma is a chronic autoimmune disease of connective tissue, characterized by microcirculatory disorders, immune inflammation, and progressive fibrosis. In recent years, the role of cytokines that regulate fibrogenesis, especially Transforming Growth Factor beta-1 (TGF- β 1), has been identified in the pathogenesis of the disease. TGF- β 1 enhances fibroblast proliferation, increases collagen synthesis, and activates extracellular matrix accumulation, which is one of the main pathogenetic mechanisms of systemic scleroderma. The aim of the study was to evaluate the effect of TGF- β 1 gene polymorphism on the clinical course and disease severity in patients with systemic scleroderma. The study involved 30 patients with systemic scleroderma and 10 healthy controls. All participants underwent clinical, laboratory, and instrumental examinations. Genetic analysis was performed using molecular genetic methods. The main polymorphic variants of the TGF- β 1 gene (T869C, G915C, and -509C/T) were studied.

According to the results, TGF- β 1 gene polymorphisms were significantly more common in patients with systemic scleroderma compared to healthy controls. Some allelic variants were associated with diffuse disease, a high degree of skin fibrosis, and interstitial damage to internal organs, especially the lungs. Patients with TGF- β 1 gene polymorphisms had a faster progression of the disease and a stronger manifestation of fibrotic changes. The results of statistical analysis showed a reliable correlation between genetic markers and clinical severity indicators ($p < 0.05$). Activation of the TGF- β 1 signaling pathway was also found to be important in assessing sensitivity to antifibrotic therapy. It was observed that early initiation of antifibrotic and immunosuppressive treatment in patients with gene polymorphisms helps to slow down the progression of the disease.

In conclusion, TGF- β 1 gene polymorphism plays an important role in the pathogenesis of systemic scleroderma and is associated with the severity of the clinical course of the disease, the degree of fibrosis, and damage to internal organs. Identification of these genetic markers is of great clinical importance in assessing the prognosis of the disease, choosing individual treatment tactics, and increasing the effectiveness of antifibrotic therapy.

Relevance

Systemic scleroderma is one of the urgent problems in modern rheumatology, characterized by a chronic progressive course of the disease, damage to internal organs, and a high degree of disability. The leading role in the pathogenesis of the disease has been identified, and the transforming growth factor - TGF- β 1 plays an important role in its development. TGF- β 1 leads to the activation of fibroblasts, increased collagen synthesis, and accumulation of extracellular matrix.

In recent years, the effect of TGF- β 1 gene polymorphisms on cytokine expression and the clinical course of the disease has been studied, but the results obtained are not uniform. The clinical significance of genetic markers, especially in patients with systemic scleroderma, has not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, determining the impact of TGF- β 1 gene

polymorphisms on the course of the disease, organ damage, and prognosis is of great scientific and practical importance..

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